

NUMERICAL MODELING OF LOW VELOCITY IMPACT RESPONSE ON METAL FOAM CORED SANDWICH PANELS: EFFECT OF VARIOUS FACESHEET MATERIALS

A. Rajaneesh, I. Sridhar* and S. Rajendran

School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, 50 Nanyang Avenue, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore 639798, Singapore

* Corresponding author (msridhar@ntu.edu.sg)

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Abstract

This paper presents a numerical modeling methodology for simulating the low velocity impact response of clamped sandwich plates consisting of aluminium foam (Alporas®) as a core and aluminium (Al) and Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) as faceplate. In present study, open-faced sandwich construction was used i.e. instead of two faced ordinary sandwich construction, only one faceplate was used. Low speed (2.65 Kg steel impactor with 6.7 m/s) impact tests were carried out on the faceplate side of sandwich plate using Instron DYNATUP 8250 apparatus. Numerical models were developed in LS-DYNA® explicit finite element software. Selection of suitable constitutive models and erosion criterion for the damage were discussed. Numerical results of load versus time and energy absorption versus time were compared with the experimental measurements.

1 Introduction

Plates are important structural elements in aerospace, ship building, and automotive industries. These areas have the requirement for low weight, high strength to stiffness. All these requirements cannot be fulfilled by simple monolithic plates. So laminated and sandwich plates becomes a better choice compared to monolithic plates in material selection. Under dynamic and localized loading, core materials acts as an energy absorbing constituent. As there are wide range manufacturing routes for metallic foams, it is important to establish their constitutive models both analytically and numerically to assess its performance under different loading conditions.

A phenomenological constitutive model for metal foams as a quadratic function of effective and mean stress was developed by Deshpande and Fleck [1] and it was implemented as *CRUSHABLE_FOAM [2] model in ABAQUS® finite element software. The same constitutive model was later modified for statistical variation in properties of foam by Hanssen *et al.* [3]. In addition, Hanssen *et al.* [3] also compared developed model with existing constitutive models (MAT_26, MAT_HONEY_COMB; MAT_63, MAT_CRUSHABLE_FOAM; MAT_75, MAT_BILKHU/DUBOIS_FOAM and MAT_126, MAT_MODIFIED_HONEYCOMB) in LS-DYNA.

For failure prediction and analysis in impact problems, in addition to the constitutive model, it is necessary to have an appropriate erosion criterion. Reyes *et al.* [4] attempted to implement different erosion/failure criteria (plastic volumetric strain, and maximum principle stress criteria with Cockcroft and Latham's energy based criterion) with Hanssen *et al.* [3] constitutive model and concluded that, maximum principal stress criterion was able to predict appropriate failure mode compared to maximum plastic volumetric strain criteria in indentation simulations. This constitutive model was implemented in LS-DYNA (MAT_154, MAT_DESHPANDE_FLECK_FOAM) with maximum volumetric strain failure criterion without statistical variation.

This paper reports numerical modeling of Alporas® foam-cored open face clamped sandwich plate with different face sheets (aluminum (Al) and carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite) subjected to low velocity impact with spherical impactor. MAT_26 was selected as a constitutive

model for foam modeling rather than MAT154. But MAT_154 does not have maximum principal stress criterion with accompanying Cockcroft and Latham's energy based criterion, which is the necessary erosion criterion for appropriate failure mode prediction under indentation loading [4].

2. Sandwich Constituents and Construction

Alporas closed cell Al alloy foam from GLEICH GmbH, Germany with an average relative density of 9.5% was used as the core material. Aluminium 1100 half hard and CFRP laminate in unidirectional configuration (manufactured from autoclave) were used as faceplate materials. For sandwich construction, all the faceplate materials were bonded to foam the core using REDUX®-332 adhesive under heat and pressure. All the required material properties of sandwich constituents and experimental results (load versus time and energy versus time) used for comparison were taken from the experimental work of Kapil [5].

3. Finite Element Modeling

All the simulations were conducted in LS-DYNA explicit finite element software [6]. Figure 1 shows a typical geometry of the computation domain and mesh discretization.

Fig. 1 Typical numerical model used for the present study. Core and faceplate are clamped around periphery of circumference.

All the parts in present work were modeled with single integration point, eight node solid elements (Constant stress solid element, ELFORM=1) because, reduced integration elements are robust choice for nonlinear analysis to overcome negative

volumes, which are prone to happen in full integration elements. In addition, easy element deletion and less computational cost are additional benefits of reduced integration elements. In spite of afore mentioned benefits, reduced integration elements suffer from nonphysical spurious/hourglass modes. To overcome this nonphysical behavior, stiffness based hourglass control is used. To avoid excessive stiffening, care was taken in post processing stage to keep hourglass energy within prescribed permissible limits (10% of peak internal energy value). In impact region, mesh was refined sufficient enough to maintain average aspect ratio ranging from 1 to 2.

Effect of adhesive is not considered in the present simulation. Tie constraints were applied between the faceplate and core. Contact between impactor and sandwich plate was established using eroding surface to surface contact. To model contact between faceplate and core after failure, eroding single surface contact was defined. Negative volumes in foam core were avoided using interior contact option for core part. Soft constraint based contact (SOFT=1) was used for simulating bare foam impact. For sandwich plate impact, segment based contact (SOFT=2) was used. Frictionless contact was used in all simulations.

Impact experiments available in literature were conducted on Dynatup 8250 machine with sandwich plate fixed in-between two square plates (one at the top and another at the bottom of the sandwich plate) with central circular area of 76mm diameter. To simulate this clamping boundary condition in LS-DYNA, all the nodes around the circumference of sandwich plate were constrained in all the degrees of freedom. Steel impactor of 13 mm diameter was simulated as a rigid punch with steel properties using MAT_RIGID constitutive model. Impactor mass 2.65 kg and initial velocity 6.7 m/s were incorporated using PART_INERTIA option.

3.1 Modeling of ALPORAS core

Core was modeled using MAT_26 (MAT_HONEYCOMB), which is a homogenized honeycomb anisotropic constitutive model. Hanssen *et al.* [3] used this honeycomb model, MAT_26, to predict the constitutive model of foam[3]. The constitutive properties of the foam are listed in Table 1. Though MAT_26 is anisotropic constitutive

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model, isotropic behavior was achieved by assigning same properties in all orthogonal directions. Modulus calculation equations are listed here for MAT_26 from [6].

$$E_{ij} = E_{iju} + \beta(E - E_{iju}) \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{ij}^{n+1^{trial}} = \sigma_{ij}^n + E_{ij} \Delta \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (2)$$

where $\beta = \max \left[\min \left(\frac{1-V}{1-VF}, 1 \right), 0 \right]$

$i, j = 1, 2 \text{ and } 3$

where E_{ij} is the current modulus in iterative calculations; E is the modulus of bulk metal; E_{iju} is the modulus of uncompressed configuration; V is the relative volume; VF is the relative volume at which honeycomb is fully compacted, σ_{ij} is the stress tensor and ε_{ij} is the strain tensor. In the present work, the same values are assigned for both E and E_{iju} , so that the same modulus is used during whole simulation.

Uniaxial compression stress strain curve used in present simulation is shown in Figure 2. To investigate the effect of locking strain (VF), i.e. volumetric strain at which foam is fully compacted, on MAT_26 response, compression test simulation was conducted on a single element cube under displacement controlled loading for $VF = 0.0, 0.2, 0.3$ and 0.4 . Results of the numerical compression test stress-strain responses are superimposed onto the experimental stress-strain curve in Figure 2. In addition, to access physical behavior of numerical compression test, simulation screenshots are shown in Figure 3.

Lateral expansion of the foam under uni-axial compression experiment was negligibly small. However, from single element numerical compression test results shown in Figure 3, it was proved that, as the value of VF increases, lateral expansion under compression increases. Same observation can be drawn from Figure 2. Sudden drop in the stress reflects the initiation of lateral expansion. Hence, to simulate real foam behavior up to 80% compressive strain, VF values between 0.0 to 0.2 should be used.

Fracture of foam is achieved by using available tensile failure strain parameter (TSEF). Iteratively

Table 1. Foam material properties data used [7].

Property	Value
Mass density	250 kg/m ³
Young's modulus	590 MPa
Poisson's ratio	0.0
Tensile strain at failure	0.35
Shear modulus	295 MPa

Fig. 2. Uniaxial compression engineering stress vs. engineering strain response.

Fig. 3. Compression simulation of single element compression test screenshots for various values of VF at 80% strain.

different values were used, to achieve appropriate failure strain value.

3.2 Faceplate Modeling

The quasi-static uniaxial tensile stress-strain curve of Al alloy face sheet is shown in Figure. 4: it shows typical elastic-perfectly plastic behavior. The properties of Al, CFRP faceplates are tabulated in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. Metal faceplates (Al-1100) were modeled using J_2 flow theory of plasticity; MAT_PIECEWISE_LINEAR_PLASTICITY; whereas composite faceplate was modeled using MAT_COMPOSITE_FAILURE_SOLID_MODEL. For composite faceplate failure, maximum principle strain criterion was implemented using MAT_ADD_EROSION.

Table 2. Properties of aluminium1100 faceplate [7].

Property	Value
Mass density	2700 kg/m ³
Young's modulus	75 GPa
Poisson's ratio	0.3
Tensile strain at failure	0.8
Yield stress	116 MPa

Fig. 4. Aluminium 1100 engineering stress-strain curve [7].

4 Results and Discussion

After numerical implementation, before accepting results, energy balance was performed to assure the simulation correctness. A typical energy balance plot observed in all simulations is shown in Fig. 5.

4.1 Bare foam impact

To identify the correct constitutive model (MAT_154 and MAT_26) and erosion criterion

Table 3. Properties of CFRP faceplate [7].

Property	Value
Mass density	1100 kg/m ³
Young's modulus (E1)	150 GPa
Young's modulus (E2, E3)	9.5 GPa
Poisson ratio (ν_{21}, ν_{31})	0.16
Poisson ratio (ν_{32})	0.45
Shear's modulus (G12, G13)	5.43 GPa
Shear's modulus (G23)	3.26 GPa
Fail strain (MAXEPS)	0.035

Fig. 5 Energy balance plot of a typical simulation.

Table 4. Material properties used in MAT_154 [7].

Property	Value
Mass density	250 kg/m ³
Young's modulus	590 MPa
Poisson ratio	0.0
Shape of yield surface (ALPHA)	2.02
Curve fit parameter (GAMMA)	0.45 MPa
Densification strain (EPSD)	2.35
Curve fit parameter (ALPHA2)	63.3GPa
Curve fit parameter (BETA)	8.29
Yield stress (SIGP)	1.8
Volumetric strain (CFAIL)	0.025

(maximum volumetric strain criterion and tensile strain failure criterion) on failure mode, impact tests

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were performed on bare foam of 20 mm and 30mm thick. It is to be noted that MAT_154 constitutive model in LS-DYNA is similar to *CRUSHABLE_FOAM in ABAQUS. The MAT_154 model parameters for the foam are obtained by curve fitting the uniaxial compression stress-strain curve and are listed in Table 4 [3, 6].

Simulation results were shown in Figure 6. It was observed that, volumetric strain erosion criterion to predict fracture was not physically reasonable. Diagonal propagation of fracture front observed in present simulations as shown in Figure 6-a, matches with similar predictions by Reyes *et al.* [4].

With appropriate selection of constitutive model, impact response (load versus time and energy absorbed versus time) was compared with that of experiments in Figure 7 and Figure 8, for foams of 20mm and 30mm thick, respectively. It was observed that, peak load was same in both 20 mm and 30 mm thick bare foam impact, but long plateau observed in 30mm thick foam, which shows energy absorption period. In addition to force versus time and energy absorbed versus time response, numerical failure mode (core shear) prediction was in good agreement with experiments.

Fig. 6. Comparison of predicted failure modes from MAT_154 and MAT_26.

4.2 Impact of sandwich plate

Sandwich plate impact was implemented with aluminium and CFRP faceplates of 0.5 mm thick

and compared with experiments in Figure 9 and Figure 10. It was observed that, peak load was higher in the case of aluminum faceplate in comparison to CFRP because of its ductility, which in turn increases the energy absorption capacity of the sandwich. However, in the case of CFRP sandwich plate, because of its brittle fracture of faceplate, peak load and energy absorption were less in comparison to aluminum sandwich. In addition to impact response, failure mode prediction was in good agreement with the experimental observations; ductile tearing of Al faceplates commuted anisotropic fracture of CFRP face sheets (not shown here).

Fig. 7. Experimental and numerical comparison of reaction force for 20 mm and 30 mm foam impact.

Fig. 8. Experimental and numerical comparison of absorbed energy for Al or CFRP faceplates as a function of core thickness.

5. Conclusion

Numerical implementation of low velocity impact response of metal foam cored open-face sandwich plate has been presented and compared with results in literature. The following conclusions can be drawn from the current work:

- The simulated force versus time and energy absorbed versus time responses are in good agreement with the experimental measurements, for both Al and CFRP faceplate constructions.

Fig. 9. Experimental and numerical implementation of 30 mm thick core with Al and CFRP faceplates.

Fig. 10. Experimental and numerical implementation of absorbed energy for 30 mm thick core with Al and CFRP faceplates.

- All selected materials and their constitutive geometries failed through penetration under the applied impact loading condition.
- With the use of LS-DYNA, experiments were numerically simulated. Appropriate selection of material model was done based on observing failure modes, which are experimentally feasible. Towards this MAT_26 was concluded to be a good choice in available material models.
- Appropriate VF value was found using compression test simulation. From compression tests, it was concluded that, negligibly small lateral expansion can be obtained with the use of zero value for VF (relative volume at which honeycomb is fully compacted).
- With selection of constitutive model and its parameters, bare foam and sandwich plate impact was done. Numerical models were able to predict appropriate failure modes and peak load values.
- It was observed that, peak load was governed by the type of faceplate but not on the thickness of the core. Energy absorbed depends on the type of core as well as the thickness of core.

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